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ABSTRACTS

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Emerging Trends in the Development of Microthermofluidic Systems for Diagnostic Applications

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Abstract: In recent times, the miniaturization of microthermofluidic systems has gained fabulous attention in science and technology because of their versatile capability to be compact, automated, integrated, and affordable miniaturized devices that are acquiescent to be incorporated into numerous microfluidic-driven biochemical and healthcare diagnostic applications. The development of a microthermofluidic system entails the amalgamation of several components and peripherals including a microprocessor/microcontroller, microheater, microsensor, recording and display unit within a compact minuscule platform that finds application predominantly in the healthcare sector essentially as a point-of-care-testing (POCT) device. Further, an accurate, steady, and consistent temperature-controlling module is fundamental and significant to transfer brisk output for continuous supervising and screening of numerous biomarkers. Prominent applications of microdevices requiring specific and susceptible temperature control include nucleic acid amplification, drug delivery, drug formulation, protein denaturation, cell/tissue culture, nanoparticle synthesis, rheology, and digital microfluidics. However, it has been noted that the laboratory-oriented typical thermal devices that are currently in use lack cutting-edge technologies, are bulky, more costly, consume more power, and dissipate more heat leading to the drawback of being used for POCT. Thus, the development of an integrated, automated, miniaturized, low-cost, rapid ramping response and IoT-enabled microthermofluidic system is the need of the hour in most clinical and diagnostic applications. Usually, these microthermofluidic systems should have a temperature sensitivity of $\pm 0.1-0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for effective and efficient bioclinical outcomes. Further, the proposed microthermofluidic system bids prospects for differentiated novel ideas to be implemented in a microfluidic temperature-based environment for diagnostic applications including screening for several virulence such as COVID-19, Rhinovirus, and SARS-COV 2.

Keywords: Microthermofluidic (MTF), biosensor, biomarker, miniaturization, internet-of-things (IoT), thermal management system, point-of-care (POC).

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